

**AN ACADEMIC PERSPECTIVE ON THE PRESENT STATE OF
ENGLISH LANGUAGE INSTRUCTION IN UZBEKISTAN'S
SECONDARY EDUCATION SYSTEM**

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Annotation. Uzbekistan is taking a progressive approach to English language instruction to equip students with the essential skills and competencies needed for success in the 21st century. Foreign language specialists have made significant progress in implementing the objectives outlined in this Resolution. They have developed a new State Educational Standard along with teaching curricula and syllabuses. Additionally, numerous teaching aids are being created.

Keywords: education, CEFR, FLT, EFL.

On December 10, 2013, the first President of the Republic of Uzbekistan, I.A. Karimov adopted the Resolution "On Measures for Further Improving the System of Foreign Language Learning" (№ 1875). [1]

From the 1990s until 2013, foreign languages were taught in our Republic from grade 5 onwards. Under the resolution of the first President of Uzbekistan I.A. Karimov No. 1875 on improving the system of teaching foreign languages, foreign language teaching/learning was introduced from the 1st grade.

In primary grades, subjects are not taught as separate subjects, and in grades 1-4, foreign language teaching is introduced based on studying the native language and other subjects.

In addition, psychologists say that grade 5 students are at a stage when their ability to learn another language is developed, etc.

It is worth mentioning about the first grades: there is a concept that in the language experience of students, only skills and competencies acquired in the native language are useful in learning a foreign language. Accordingly, since writing in the native language is studied for the first time, writing in a foreign language begins in grade 2.

Indeed, in grades 5-6, there is a need to address the issue of learning a foreign language a little more broadly. 5th-grade students begin to learn a

foreign language based on the principle of oral speech progression. This means that any language unit being studied (conscious speech unit) is first mastered in listening and speaking, and after a certain time, it is also practiced in written speech. The progression of oral speech varies in different methodological systems: the interval can be 3 hours or 1 month, and even in some foreign methodologists, for example, in the system of Harold Palmer, it is extended to 6 months). Palmer called this period the incubation period. Various psychological factors are considered when determining the period between oral and written speech.

In Uzbekistan, all individuals are guaranteed equal rights to education, irrespective of gender, race, nationality, language, religion, social origin, beliefs, or personal and social status. Education is compulsory in Uzbekistan. The stages of general secondary education (grades I-XI) include:

- Primary education: grades I-IV
- Basic secondary education: grades V-IX
- Secondary education: grades X-XI

In Uzbekistan, secondary and specialized education focuses on mastering the general education curricula established by the State Educational Standard. This education aims to develop knowledge, skills, and abilities that are adapted to the national context, based on the Common European Framework of Reference for Languages.[2]

The document «Common European Framework of Reference for Languages: Learning, Teaching, Assessment» (CEFR) was created by the Council of Europe.[3]

In the CEFR document, the reference of six levels is given and designed as illustrative descriptors (scales) in terms of «*Can Do*» statements from levels A1 to C2. These scales can be used as a tool for comparing levels of ability amongst learners of FL and also offer «a means to map the progress» of learners.[4]

Learning Modern languages throughout a whole life proposes six common reference levels of education:

Table 1. **Look at the**

C2	Mastery	Proficient user
C1	Effective Operational Proficiency	

B2 B1	Vantage Threshold	Independent user
A2 A1	Breakthrough Waystage	Basic user

Acquiring each stage successively learners have real opportunity to communicate with people of other language contexts.

The CEFR document enhances the transparency of courses, syllabuses, and qualifications, thus promoting international cooperation in the field of Modern languages which requires mutual recognition of qualifications gained in different learning contexts and aids in promoting students’ mobility. According to the CEFR, learners of every LT context should be facilitated to gain a particular proficiency level in a particular stage of learning.

The domestic multistage model of continuous and successive FLT includes the levels of FL presented in Table 2.[5]

Table 2. The stages and levels of FL

Educational stage	Classes	Levels according to CEFR
Primary and Secondary education	1-4 forms at school	A1
	5-9 forms at school	A2
	10-11 forms at school	B1
Professional Education	Academic lyceums 1-3 courses	B1+
	Vocational colleges	
	Language-oriented academic lyceums	B1+
Higher education	Bachelor's degrees from non-linguistic institutes and universities	B2
	Master’s degree non-linguistic institutes and universities	
	The second language in Bachelor's and Master's degree institutions and universities	
	Bachelor's degree in linguistic institutes and universities	C1
	Master's degree linguistic institutes and universities	

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